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Final report on biobank activities completed

Deliverable Report

D8.10

WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level

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2 Glossary

1-hydroxynaphthalene	1-OHNAP
1-hydroxypyrene	1-OHP
2-ethyl-5-hydroxyhexyl phthalate	5OH-MEPH
2-ethyl-5-oxohexyl phthalate	5oxo-MEHP
2-hydroxynaphthalene	2-OHNAP
6-OH-Mono-propyl-heptyl phthalate	OH-MiDP
7-Carboxy-(mono-methylheptyl) phthalate	cx-MiNP
7-OH-(Mono-methyl-octyl) phthalate	OH-MiNP
Bis(1,3-dichloro-2-propyl) phosphate	BDCIPP
Bis(1-chloro-2-propyl) phosphate	BCIPP
Bis(2-chloroethyl) phosphate	BCEP
Bisphenol A, S, F	BPA, S, F
Cadmium	Cd
Creatinine	Cr
Cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylate-mono-(7-carboxylate-4-methyl)heptyl ester	cx-MINCH
Cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylate-mono-(7-hydroxy-4-methyl)octyl ester	OH-MINCH
Di(2-propylheptyl) phthalate	DPHP
Di-isononylcyclohexane 1,2-dicarboxylate	DiNCH
Mono(2,7-methyl-7-carboxy-heptyl) phthalate	cx-MiDP
Mono(2-ethyl-5-carboxypentyl) phthalate	5cx-MEPP
Mono(n-pentyl) phthalate	MnPeP
Monobenzyl phthalate	MBzP
Mono-cyclo-hexyl phthalate	MCHP
Monoethyl phthalate	MEP
Monoethylhexyl phthalate	MEHP
Monoisobutyl phthalate	MiBP
Mono-n-butyl phthalate	MnBP
Mono-n-octyl phthalate	MnOP
Mono-n-pentyl phthalate	MnPeP
Organophosphate flame retardants	OPFR
Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons	PAH

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3 Abstract/Summary

The aim of Task 8.2 is to investigate data sources and evaluate time trends in chemical exposure across Europe. The ambition was to collect exposure data for three time points (2003-2010, 2011-2013, 2014-2019/2020), in two population groups (children and adults) and across four geographical regions.

This is the final report for Task 8.2 and summarises all the activities and data analysis undertaken since the publication of AD8.5. These activities include the literature search for data covering the first time point and the progresses made in the new analyses of DEMOCOPHES biobank samples.

Information on chemical exposure for the first time point was obtained from published exposure data available in the literature, while data for the second and third time point was based on new analyses of DEMOCOPHES biobank samples and data generated by the HBM aligned studies in Task 8.1, respectively.

The purpose of this work is to answer specific policy questions such as: do regulated chemicals show a decline in exposure trends. The data generated through these time trend analyses will allow us to answer to policy questions posed in the annual work programmes.

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4 Introduction

The aim of Work Package 8 (WP8) is to collect biomonitoring data across Europe to determine exposure to the HBM4EU 1st and 2nd priority list of chemicals in the general population or in an occupational setting. In Task 8.2, the specific objectives are to collect and generate Human Biomonitoring (HBM) data for certain selected substances on the HBM4EU 1st priority list for three different time points, in four geographical regions of Europe, and two target populations, to facilitate the analysis of time trends in chemical exposure.

Chemical exposure was assessed for three time points: 2003-2010, 2011-2013 and 2014-2019/2020, using three different strategies. Time point 1 (2003-2010), consisted of published HBM data which was identified through literature search. For time point 2 (2011-2013), DEMOCOPHES biobank samples were accessed for retrospective analysis of chemical exposure and time point 3 (2014-2019/2020) utilised new harmonised HBM data collected in Task 8.1 (alignment of national studies).

The work focused on two population groups (children aged 6-11 years and adult women aged 20-45 years) in four geographical regions of Europe (north, south, east, and west). Using this data, we aimed to assess time patterns for the following substances included in the 1st list of priority substances: Di-isononylcyclohexane 1,2-dicarboxylate (DiNCH), bisphenols, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH), organophosphate flame retardants (OPFR), phthalates and cadmium (Cd)

The aim of this report is to summarise all Task 8.2 activities performed from 2017 up to October 2021.

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5 Data collection strategy

5.1 Description of work

This report provides a summary of all the Task 8.2 activities completed from 2017 through to 2021. Throughout the course of the project, this work has been described in more detail in Deliverable Report 8.2: First Report on Biobank Activities, Deliverable Report 8.6: Second Report on Biobank Activities, and Additional Deliverable Report 8.5: Summary Report of Task 8.2 Activities.

5.1.1 Prioritised substances

The substances selected for time trend analysis were chosen based on i) being on the HBM4EU 1st list of priority chemicals and ii) that they could be analysed in urine. The rationale for the limitation to only one matrix is that the biobank samples from the DEMOCOPHES study is limited to urine samples. Information on the selected substances, their metabolites of interest, and target population(s) is outlined in Table 1.

5.1.2 Time points for time trend analysis

Urine biomonitoring data was collected and analysed for the following three time points.

1. 2003-2010 (extended from 2006-2010 in 2021)
2. 2011-2013
3. 2014-2019/2020

For the first time point, we used exposure data identified through literature search or from the aggregated data already obtained within HBM4EU. Due to the limited number of studies matching the time and study population criteria, the search was later extended to include studies with sampling year starting from 2003. The search strategy and the results of the literature search has been described in detail in the Additional Deliverable Report 8.5: Summary Report of Task 8.2 Activities. For the second time point, new analyses of DEMOCOPHES biobank urine sampled were undertaken, and for the third time point, new harmonised data collected in Task 8.1 (alignment of studies) was utilised.

5.1.3 Target population

In alignment with the population groups sampled in the DEMOCOPHES study and two of the age groups included in the Task 8.1 alignment studies, the Task 8.2 work focused on two population groups:

- Children 6-11 years
- Adult women 20-45 years (to be compared with women aged 20-39 years in the aligned studies).

5.1.4 European geographical regions

Urine biomonitoring data was collected for four geographical regions in alignment with the categorisation described in Deliverable report 8.1: A strategy to collect EU wide HBM data:

- North: Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Iceland, Ireland, Latvia, Lithuania, Norway, Sweden, UK
- South: Croatia, Cyprus, Greece, Italy, Malta, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain
- East: Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Slovakia
- West: Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Luxembourg, The Netherlands, Switzerland

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Table 1: List of substances on the HBM4EU 1st list of priority chemicals that were selected for time trend analysis, their metabolites and target populations.

Substance	Metabolites	Target population
DiNCH	OH-MINCH, cx-MINCH	Children
OPFR	DPHP, BDCIPP, BCEP, BCIPP	Children
Bisphenols	BPA, BPF, BPS	Women
PAHs	1-OHNAP, 2-OHNAP, 1-OHP	Women
Phthalates	MEHP, 5OH-MEHP, 5oxo-MEHP, 5cx-MEPP, MEP, MBzP, MiBP, MnBP, MCHP, MnPeP, MnOP, OH-MiNP, cx-MiNP, OH-MiDP, cx-MiDP	Children
Cd	Not applicable	Women

5.1.5 Time trend analysis

Due to delays caused by Covid-19, the statistical analysis has been delayed and therefore not reported in this deliverable as was originally planned. It is now scheduled to be conducted, in collaboration with Work Package 10 (WP10, data management), during fall 2021.

The initial plan was to conduct a time trend analysis, which is an analysis that aims at controlling as many variables as possible (age of participants, study setup), while evaluating changes in chemical exposure over time. However, given that the three time points included in the time trend are all based on studies that differ with respect to country, recruitment protocols, sampling strategy, study population, laboratory and their quality assessments, and that literature data may not be available for some substances for the first time point, the feasibility of conducting such analysis is questionable. At a meeting in 2019, the statistical working group in WP10, therefore decided that the time trend data will instead be analysed as aggregated data in a descriptive way, from here on referred to as time patterns, rather than at the individual level as time trends.

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6 Results

6.1 Time point 1: Literature search

6.1.1 DiNCH

Limited data on DiNCH was found in the literature search, and of those studies identified, that were within the correct time frame and region, none assessed exposure in children, which is the target population for DiNCH. Therefore, it is not possible to perform time patterns, using data from all three time points for DiNCH.

6.1.2 OPFRs

Like DiNCH, there was a clear lack of OPFR urine biomonitoring data published, that was sampled within the specified time period, within the European region and in the right target population. Thus, it will not be possible to complete time patterns for OPFRs using data from all the three time points.

6.1.3 Bisphenols

Studies providing urine biomonitoring data on bisphenols in women, within the relevant time frame was identified for the north, west and south geographical regions. No data were available for the east region. Bisphenol A (BPA) was the most commonly reported of the three (bisphenol) metabolites. In total, data from four studies were extracted, two from the north region (Sweden, BPA, BPS and BPF) (Gyllenhammar et al. 2017), one from the west region (Netherlands, BPA BPS and BPF) (Philips et al. 2020) and one from the south region (Spain, BPA) (Casas et al. 2011). Table 2 provides a summary of all studies reporting bisphenol exposure information from which data was extracted.

6.1.4 PAHs

All studies that were identified in the literature search that were within the relevant time frame and target population, provided urine biomonitoring data on PAH for only 1-hydroxypyrene (1-OHP). Data on 1-OHP was extracted from six studies, covering the north (UK) (Aquilina et al. 2010), east (Poland) (Polanska et al. 2014) and the south geographical regions (Spain) (Bartolome et al. 2015; Llop et al. 2008). For one study (Bartolome et al. 2015), harmonised aggregated data already available within the HBM4EU was used. Table 2 provides a summary of all the identified studies from which the assessed PAH exposure data was extracted.

6.1.5 Phthalates

Several studies were identified in the literature search which reported biomonitoring data on phthalates within the stipulated time frame, geographical region, and target population. Data from seven studies were extracted, representing three of the four geographical regions: the north (Denmark (Boas et al. 2010; Frederiksen et al. 2014)), the west (Austria (Wallner et al. 2016), Germany (Becker et al. 2009; Kasper-Sonnenberg et al. 2012; Koch et al. 2011)), and the south region (Spain) (Casas et al. 2011). For two studies (Becker et al. 2009; Frederiksen et al. 2014), harmonised aggregated data already available within the HBM4EU was used. No data matching the time and target population criteria were identified for the east region. These studies are summarised in Table 2.

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6.1.6 Cd

Urine biomonitoring data on Cd matching the time and target population criteria were only identified for two of the four target regions. Exposure data was extracted from eight studies representing the west (France (Béchaux et al. 2014; Nisse et al. 2017) , Germany (Heitland and Köster 2006)) and south (Spain (Aguilera et al. 2008; López-Herranz et al. 2016; Sánchez-Rodríguez et al. 2015), Italy (Ranzi et al. 2013) and Slovenia (Snoj Tratnik et al. 2019)) geographical regions. For two studies, (López-Herranz et al. 2016; Snoj Tratnik et al. 2019), harmonised aggregated data already available within the HBM4EU was used. These studies are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2: Biomonitoring studies assessing exposure to HBM4EU first priority substances during the first time point in the European population identified through literature search

Country	Median urine concentration ^a	Analytical technique	Population	Year of data collection	Reference
DiNCH					
North					
No studies identified	-	-	-	-	-
West					
No studies identified	-	-	-	-	-
East					
No studies identified	-	-	-	-	-
South					
No studies identified	-	-	-	-	-
OPFR					
North					
No studies identified	-	-	-	-	-
West					
No studies identified	-	-	-	-	-
East					
No studies identified	-	-	-	-	-
South					
No studies identified	-	-	-	-	-

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Country	Median urine concentration ^a	Analytical technique	Population	Year of data collection	Reference
Bisphenols					
North					
Sweden	0.08 -1.29 ^{b,c} µg/L (0.08-1.29 ng/mL)	LC-MS/MS	27 adult women, 20-41 years	2009	Gyllenhammar et al. 2017
Sweden	(0.07-1.15 ^{b,c} µg/L) (0.07-1.15 ng/mL)	LC-MS/MS	30 adult women, 20-41 years	2010	Gyllenhammar et al. 2017
West					
The Netherlands	0.09-0.38 ^b µg/L (0.24-1.67 nmol/L)	HPLC-ESI-MS/MS	1213 pregnant women, mean age of 30 years	2004-2005	Philips et al. 2020
East					
No studies identified	-	-	-	-	-
South					
Spain	2.2 µg/L (2.2 ng/mL)	HPLC-MS/MS	120 pregnant women	2004-2008	Casas et al. 2011
PAHs					
North					
UK	0.13 µg/L (0.13 pg/µL)	LC-MS/MS	100 adults, 18-66 years	2005-2007	Aquilina et al. 2010
West					
No studies identified	-	-	-	-	-
East					
Poland	0.25 µg/g cr	GC-MS	210 pregnant women, 20-40 years	2007-2011	Polanska et al. 2014
South					
Spain	0.13 µg/g cr	HPLC-FD	993 adults, 16-65 years	2009-2010	Bartolomé et al. 2015d
Spain	0.12 µg/g cr (0.061 µmol/mol cr)	HPLC-FD	204 pregnant women, 16-36+ years	2003-2005	Llop et al. 2008

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Country	Median urine concentration ^a	Analytical technique	Population	Year of data collection	Reference
Phthalates					
North					
Denmark	0-36b µg/g cr	LC-MS/MS	845 children, 4-9 years	2006-2007	Boas et al. 2010
Denmark	0.7-80.6 µg/L (0.7-80.6b ng/mL)	LC-MS/MS	129 children and adolescents, 6-21 years	2007	Frederiksen et al. 2014d
West					
Austria	0.9-28b µg/g cr	LC-ESI-MS/MS	50 children (boys), mean age of 8 years	2009	Wallner et al. 2016
Germany	0.09-42.3b µg/g cr	LC/LC-MS/MS	465 children, 8-10 years	2007-2008 and 2009-2010	Kaspersen-Sonnenberg et al. 2014
West					
Germany	6.7-93.4 ^b µg/L	LC/LC-MS/MS	1790 children, 3-14 years	2003-2006	Becker et al. 2009 ^d
Germany	0.7-42.8 ^b µg/L	LC/LC-MS/MS	111 children, 5-6 years	2007	Koch et al. 2011
East					
No studies identified	-	-	-	-	-
South					
Spain	6.2-755 ^b µg/L (6.2-755 ng/mL)	HPLC-MS/MS	30 children, 4 years old	2005-2006	Casas et al. 2011
Cd					
North					
No studies identified	-	-	-	-	-
West					
France	0.36 µg/L	ICP-MS	1910 adults, 20-59 years	2008-2010	Nisse et al. 2017
France	0.33 ^e µg/g cr	Not described	1900 adults, 18-74 years	2006-2007	Bechaux et al. 2014
Germany	0.42 ^f µg/L	ICP-MS	159 adults, adolescents and children, 2-65 years	2005	Heitland et al. 2006
East					
No studies identified	-	-	-	-	-

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Country	Median urine concentration ^a	Analytical technique	Population	Year of data collection	Reference
South					
Spain	0.373 µg/L	DRC-ICP-MS	45 adults, 25-45 years	2007-2010	Sánchez-Rodríguez et al. 2015
Spain	0.20 µg/L	DRC-ICP-MS	1892 adults, 18-65 years	2009-2010	Lopez Herranz et al. 2016 ^d
Spain	0.57/0.65 ^g µg/L	AAS	1718 adults, 18-69 years	2003-2004	Aguilera et al. 2010
Italy	0.16 µg/L	ICP-MS	103 adults, mean age of 48 years	2010	Ranzi et al. 2013
South					
Slovenia	0.19 µg/L	ICP-MS	189 pregnant women and their partners, 23-44 years	2008-2009	Tratnik et al. 2019 ^d

Abbreviations: LC-MS/MS: liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry; LC/LC-MS/MS: multidimensional liquid chromatography coupled tandem mass spectrometry; HPLC-ESI-MS/MS: high performance liquid chromatography electrospray ionisation-tandem mass spectrometry; HPLC-MS/MS: high-performance liquid chromatography-isotope dilution tandem mass spectrometry; HPLC-FD: high resolution liquid chromatography with fluorimetric detection; GC-MS: gas chromatography/mass spectrometry; LC/LC-MS/MS: multidimensional liquid chromatography coupled tandem mass spectrometry; LC-ESI-MS/MS: liquid chromatography-electrospray ionisation-tandem mass spectrometry; ICP-MS: inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer; DRC-ICP-MS: dynamic reaction cell inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer; AAS: atomic absorption spectrometry

a = Harmonised data format (in format as originally reported in the literature)

b = Range of medians for each substance/metabolite measured

c = Adjusted for specific density

d = Harmonised aggregated data already available within HBM4EU and data in time patterns are included as such.

e = Female median value, combined median value unavailable

f = 95th percentile, 50th percentile (median) value unavailable

g = Ria of Huelva population/other Andalusian capital cities, combined median unavailable

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6.2 Time point 2: DEMOCOPHES biobank samples

In 2015, BPA exposure data (in a subset of countries), seven phthalate metabolites and Cd in the DEMOCOPHES study were assessed and published (Covaci et al. 2015; Den Hond et al. 2015). For the remaining priority substances, new analyses of DEMOCOPHES biobank samples were undertaken in 2019, 2020 and the first half of 2021. Ten partners expressed an interest in performing new analyses, and at present, the results have been reported to the data management team by most partners and for the majority of the selected substances. A summary of the completed and planned analyses is outlined in Table 3.

Table 3: Summary of the completed and planned laboratory analyses of HBM4EU 1st priority substances in the DEMOCOPHES biobank samples

Partner	Number of samples/Children	Number of samples/ Women
North		
Denmark/UCPH		
DiNCH	143	Not analysed ^a
OPFR	Not analysed	Not analysed ^a
Bisphenols	143 ^a (BPA)	145 (BPA), (BPF, BPS not analysed)
PAHs	Not analysed ^a	Not analysed
Phthalates	143	145 ^a
Cd	143 ^a	144
Sweden/SEPA/KI ^b		
DiNCH	99	94 ^a
OPFR	99	94 ^a
Bisphenols	98 ^a (BPA), 99 ^a (BPF, BPS)	98 (BPA), 94 (BPF, BPS)
PAHs	99 ^a	94
Phthalates	98	98 ^a
Cd	100 ^a	100
West		
Belgium/VITO		
DiNCH	117	Not analysed ^a
OPFR	117	Not analysed ^a
Bisphenols	129 ^a (BPA)	129 (BPA), 117 (BPF, BPS)
PAHs	Not analysed ^a	Not analysed
Phthalates	129	129 ^a
Cd	129 ^a	129

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Partner	Number of samples/Children	Number of samples/ Women
Germany/UBA		
DiNCH	113	Not analysed ^a
OPFR	112	Not analysed ^a
Bisphenols	Not analysed ^a	Not analysed
PAHs	Not analysed ^a	114
Phthalates	120	120 ^a
Cd	119 ^a	112
Luxembourg/LNS		
DiNCH	59	Not analysed ^a
OPFR	Not analysed	Not analysed ^a
Bisphenols	60 ^a (BPA)	60 (BPA), 57 (BPF, BPS)
PAHs	Not analysed ^a	59
Phthalates	60	60 ^a
Cd	60 ^a	60
East		
Czech Republic/MU/SZU-CZ		
DiNCH	118	Not analysed ^a
OPFR	116	Not analysed ^a
Bisphenols	Not analysed ^a	BPA/BPF/BPS: 116
PAHs	Not analysed ^a	116
Phthalates	120	120 ^a
Cd	120 ^a	120
Poland/NIOM		
DiNCH	94	Not analysed ^a
OPFR	Not analysed	Not analysed ^a
Bisphenols	Not analysed ^a	93 (BPA), (BPF, BPS not analysed)
PAHs	Not analysed ^a	93
Phthalates	120	120 ^a
Cd	120 ^a	120
Hungary/NPHI		
DiNCH	Not analysed	Not analysed ^a
OPFR	Not analysed	Not analysed ^a
Bisphenols	Not analysed ^a	Not analysed
PAHs	Not analysed ^a	Not analysed
Phthalates	120	120 ^a
Cd	120 ^a	120

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Partner	Number of samples/Children	Number of samples/ Women
Slovakia/UVZ		
DiNCH	Not analysed	Not analysed ^a
OPFR	Not analysed	Not analysed ^a
Bisphenols	Not analysed ^a	Not analysed
PAHs	Not analysed ^a	Not analysed
Phthalates	129	129 ^a
Cd	129 ^a	129
South		
Cyprus/ MOH-CY		
DiNCH	60	Not analysed ^a
OPFR	60	Not analysed ^a
Bisphenols	Not analysed ^a	BPA/BPF/BPS: 60
PAHs	Not analysed ^a	60
Phthalates	60	60
Cd	60	60
Slovenia/JSI		
DiNCH	Not analysed ^a	Not analysed
OPFR	115	Not analysed ^a
Bisphenols	112 ^a (BPA), (BPF, BPS not analysed)	107 (BPA), (BPF, BPS not analysed)
PAHs	Not analysed ^a	Not analysed
Phthalates	120	120 ^a
Cd	120 ^a	120
Spain/ISCIII		
DiNCH	120	Not analysed ^a
OPFR	Not analysed	Not analysed ^a
Bisphenols	119 ^a (BPA), (BPF, BPS not analysed)	115 (BPA), 117 (BPF, BPS)
PAHs	Not analysed ^a	Not analysed
Phthalates	120	120 ^a
Cd	120 ^a	120

a = Not target group for substance, analysis not required

b = Analyses have been completed, but outside HBM4EU QA/QC scheme (analysed at ULUND)

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6.3 Time point 3: Aligned studies

The data collection and the analyses of HBM4EU first priority substances in the aligned studies is completed for almost all substances and countries, with the only exception being the analysis of PAH in the samples from Portugal, for which the results are expected within the next few months. Table 4 provides a summary of all completed and planned (where applicable) laboratory analyses of HBM4EU first priority substances in Task 8.1 aligned studies.

Table 4: Summary of the completed and planned laboratory analyses of HBM4EU first priority substances the in Task 8.1 aligned studies

Analytical status	Number of studies	Number of samples/children	Number of samples/women
DiNCH			
North			
Completed	2	600	Not analysed
West			
Completed	4	807	Not analysed
East			
Completed	3	862	Not analysed
South			
Completed	3	610	Not analysed
OPFR			
North			
Completed	2	591	Not analysed
West			
Completed	3	732	Not analysed
East			
Completed	1	300	Not analysed
South			
Completed	1	147	Not analysed
Bisphenols			
North			
Completed	3	Not analysed	386
West			
Completed	4	Not analysed	420
East			
Completed	2	Not analysed	306
South			
Completed	2	Not analysed	330

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Analytical status	Number of studies	Number of samples/children	Number of samples/women
PAHs			
North			
Completed	2	Not analysed	208
West			
Completed	4	Not analysed	533
East			
Completed	2	Not analysed	311
South			
Completed	1	Not analysed	159
Planned	1	-	171
Phthalates			
North			
Completed	2	600	Not analysed
West			
Completed	4	808	Not analysed
East			
Completed	3	858	Not analysed
South			
Completed	3	609	Not analysed
Cd			
North			
Completed	2	Not analysed	233
West			
Completed	3	Not analysed	471
East			
Completed	2	Not analysed	313
South			
Completed	2	Not analysed	330

6.4 Time patterns

When the time pattern analysis is completed, it will be possible to visualise the results using the European Human Biomonitoring Dashboard (<https://www.hbm4eu.eu/eu-hbm-dashboard/>). Results of the time patterns will also be disseminated in D8.11: Final report on new targeted studies.

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7 Considerations

Based on the results of the literature review, published exposure data was limited for many of the prioritised substances. No exposure data was found for DiNCH and OPFRs, while for bisphenols, PAHs, phthalates and Cd, exposure data was only available for some regions. This will impact on the number of time points that can be assessed in the final time pattern analysis for each region and substance.

When comparing exposure data from the three time points it is important to consider that while the DEMOCOPHES and aligned studies are fairly comparable with respect to study population, laboratory (all samples were analysed in laboratories that successfully passed the quality assurance program established by WP9, and in that way are harmonised), the exposure data gathered from the literature originate from studies which differ to varying degrees. As an example, while there were only slight differences in study population between the DEMOCOPHES and aligned studies (DEMOCOPHES non-pregnant women aged 20-45 years and the in aligned studies non-pregnant women aged 20-39 years), the study population giving rise to the literature data covered both wider age spans (16-74 years) as well as both pregnant and non-pregnant women. Regarding laboratory, the quantification techniques used in the studies identified in the literature were similar across studies and per substance and involved, with only few deviations; High-Performance Liquid Chromatography with Fluorescence Detection (HPLC-FD) for PAH, inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (ICP-MS) for Cd and multidimensional liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry (LC/LC-MS/MS) for phthalates.

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8 Conclusion

The central tenant of HBM4EU is to develop science to support policy development and evaluation. Analysis of time patterns, rather than time trends, will be performed for all prioritised substances for as many geographical regions and time points as data allow.

The evaluation of time trends/ patterns will allow us to answer a number of policy questions:

1. Are there different time trends for unregulated (DEP, DMP, DCHP, DPHP) and regulated phthalates (DEHP, BBzP, DnBP, DiBP, DinP, DnOP) and Hexamoll® DINCH®?
2. Is there a significant time trend of Cd and PAH levels in existing population studies?
3. How effective have the different mitigation steps and regulations been for phthalates?
 - a. Had the restriction under REACH have a favourable impact, that is a reduction of GM/median concentrations of the already restricted phthalates (DEHP, BBzP, DnBP, DiNP, DiDP, DnOP), especially for children from 2007 until today (2018-2021)?
 - b. Was the introduction of the Authorisation obligation under REACH effective enough to protect European citizen? Is there a sufficient decrease of the Cat. A substance levels subject to authorisation (GM/median) in the European population (general/children) from year 2015 until today (2018-2021) (i.e. DEHP, DnBP, DiBP, BBzP)? Are there differences between countries?
 - c. Had the identification as SVHC already an impact on the reduction of the phthalate exposure of the population (i.e. Did the exposure of a certain substance decline after the substance is identified as SVHC)?
4. What are current HBM levels of legacy/regulated OPFR? How do these compare to any historical records? Is the current legislative framework and proposed actions leading to a significant decline in restricted compounds and is this uniform across the EU?

For each data collection, exposure distributions based on descriptive statistics will be used. For the 2nd and 3rd time points, R-scripts developed by VITO were used to calculate aggregated HBM data, presented as percentiles (P05, P10, P25, P50, P75, P90, P95). Percentiles were also requested from literature data. Exposure distributions will be visualised per data collection, per time point, allowing for a graphical comparison of the obtained HBM data over time, and statistical analyses on the aggregated data.

The statistical analysis will be performed during fall/winter 2021 and the final results will be available on the European Human Biomonitoring Dashboard and disseminated in D8.11: Final report on new targeted studies.

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